

CLEANING WATER FROM ERYTHROMYCIN BY MEANS OF WASTE BIOMASS

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ABSTRACT

The main effects of pollution in aquatic systems include adverse effects on water quality, destruction of natural habitats of aquatic organisms, acute and sub-acute toxic effects for their health and by extension on human health, etc. The ability of plants to remove contaminants from the environment has been widely recognised over the last decades (Wuana et al., 2010) and relevant technologies are continuously developing.

For the removal of erythromycin (a persistent antibiotic) from surrogate wastewater, water-soluble erythromycin 5% (Erythromycin thiocyanate 5g, excipients 100g) was used. The antibiotic was in the form of powder and is typically supplied as an additive to birds' drinking water. Experiments were conducted, with a number of species, some of which are shown in Table 1. Stems of those were collected from a wood near Acheloos river in the region of Agrinio (38 37'00" N 21 24"00E/38.6167 N), Aetoloacarnania, Greece.

Table 1. Typical species used for erythromycin removal from surrogate wastewaters

Species	Treatment (days)	Stems(No)	L, cm	Leaves	V _{initial} ml	ΔV _{ave} , ml
<i>Willow Salix sp</i>	18	2	45	NLV	400 /TW	240
orange tree <i>Citrus sp</i>	18	2	45	NLV	400 /TW	250
Sowthistle <i>Sonchus sp.</i>	25	4	19	LVT	100/ TW	18
Bamboo <i>Fargesia sp.</i>	14	4	30	LVT	700 / UP	20
Charlock <i>Sinapis sp.</i>	6	20		LV	175/ TW	20

Table 1 shows the length of treatment in days, the number of stems put in different glass recipients with solution, or as references, the initial length L of each stem in cm, whether the submerged stem had leaves (LV), or not-without leaves-(NLV) or with leaves on the top (out of the solution) only (LVT). In the one but the last column the initial volume of solution V_{initial} (in mL) and the kind of the water used for the solution is shown, tap water, TW, or ultra-pure, UW, water. The last column displays the contaminated water volume removal. The initial concentration of erythromycin in the solution was 4 g L⁻¹.

The first three species demonstrated a high water capacity removal. Moreover, UV absorption nine days after the treatment was reduced by approximately 30%-50%, indicating that selective removal of organic matter was achieved

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References:

Wuana R.A., Okieimen F.E. and Imborvungu J.A., "Removal of heavy metals from a contaminated soil using organic chelating acids. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 7:485-496 (2010).